

Kinetics of Oxidation of Glutamic Acid by Sodium-N-Chloro-4-Methyl Benzene Sulphonamide in Hydrochloric Acid Medium*

S. N. KATGERI, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and H. M. K. NAIDU

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Manasa Gangotri, Mysore-570 006

Manuscript received 30 April 1979, revised 13 March 1980, accepted 31 March 1980

A kinetic study of oxidation of glutamic acid in hydrochloric acid medium has been made at 30°. The reaction is found to be first order with respect to chloramine-T, glutamic acid and H⁺ ion. Ionic strength, addition of chloride ion and presence of reaction product, *p*-toluene sulphonamide have negligible effect on the reaction rate. The reaction was studied at different temperatures and activation parameters have been evaluated. A mechanism in which the zwitter ion interacts with protonated CAT has been proposed to account for the observed kinetics.

SODIUM-N-chloro-4-methyl benzene sulphonamide or chloramine-T (*p*-CH₃-C₆H₄SO₂NCI Na. 3 H₂O, CAT) behaves as an oxidizing agent both in acid and alkaline media¹⁻². This organic compound containing positive halogen undergoes a two electron change in its reactions. The oxidation potential of chloramine-T/sulphonamide system is *pH* dependent and decreases with an increase in *pH* of the medium. Although chloraminometric oxidation of bio-organic compounds has been reported in literature, only a few of these reactions in alkaline medium have been kinetically investigated^{3,4}. As a part of our kinetic studies of chloraminometric reactions in acid medium⁵, we report our investigations on the reaction of glutamic acid with CAT in hydrochloric acid medium.

Glutamic acid is a non-essential amino acid present in all complete proteins. The mono sodium salt—L(+) sodium glutamate finds extensive use commercially as flavouring intensifier. Glutamic acid itself is used in medicine, biochemical research, salt substituent and as a dietary supplement. Glutamic acid undergoes oxidation by CAT in presence of HCl with a four electron change. The reaction was fast in HCl of over-all concentration 0.01 to 0.1M at 25°.

Experimental

Reagents used, their standardisation, kinetic runs as also the stoichiometry and product determinations have been the same as described earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

The experimental rate law is of the form :

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = k[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+][\text{glutamic acid}] \dots (1)$$

Ionic strength, addition of chloride ion and presence of the reaction product, *p*-toluene sulphonamide have negligible effect on the reaction rate.

Scheme-I may be proposed to account for the observed kinetics : (cf. Ref. No. 6)

Scheme I

Assuming steady state condition for RNHCl and with the reasonable assumption that $k_{-1} \gg k_2[\text{S}^{\ominus}]$ the rate law can be shown to be

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}}[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+][\text{S}^{\ominus}] = k[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+][\text{S}] \dots (2)$$

which is in agreement with equation (1) and the experimental results. Further, it is noted that a change in the solvent composition by adding methanol to reaction mixture affects the rate. The retardation of rate by the added methanol could indicate the dipole-dipole nature of reactants shown in step (III) of Scheme-I. The value of the enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H^{\ddagger}$, 73.3 KJ mole⁻¹; $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$, -31.0 JK⁻¹) observed during this reaction is comparable to those obtained during the oxidation of leucine and other amino acids by CAT where the formation of chlorinated amino acid intermediates is assumed. The negative entropy of activation lends support to the formation of a more compact intermediate X as shown in the mechanistic step. The mechanism is further supported by the stoichiometry of the reaction.

*Paper presented at the 66th Annual Session of the Indian Science Congress, January 3-7, 1979.

Scheme II

A detailed mechanism of oxidation of glutamic acid by CAT is given in Scheme II

Acknowledgement

One of us (S.N.K.) thanks the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for a grant under the Faculty Improvement Programme.

References

1. A. BERKA, T. VULTERIN and J. ZYKA, "Newer Redox Titrants", Pergamon, New York, 1965, p. 37.
2. V. J. JENNINGS, "CRC Critical Reviews in Analytical Chemistry", 1974, p. 407.
3. A. KUMAR, A. K. BOSE and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1975, 106, 13.
4. A. K. BOSE, R. M. MEHROTRA and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 896.
5. N. M. M. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1979, 110, 157.
6. H.M.K. NAIDU, S.N. KATGERI and D.S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1185.